

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR USING MODERN MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article is intended for learning intended for the use of multimedia educational resources and methods using modern information technologies used in the educational process, independent use and comprehensive use of educational materials.*

Keywords: *multimedia, multimedia technology, animation, multimedia applications, videos, interactive, information educational resources.*

At present, the amount of information generated and processed during the period of informatization of the educational system is increasing day by day, modern computers and telecommunication technologies are rapidly improving, and in the same conditions it is necessary to provide the educational system with the necessary sources of information. The formation of knowledge and skills is one of the important tasks. At the same time, modern information technology tools in the educational process are completely changing and all their capabilities are being created, as well as more opportunities are being created for the implementation of modern methods, methods and software tools of new pedagogical technologies.

To prove these opinions, a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 23, 2001 "Development of computer and information technologies in 2001-2005, measures to organize the development of a program to ensure the wide penetration of the Internet into international information systems" was adopted. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2002 No. 230 "On the further development of informatization and the introduction of information and communication technologies" and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 6, 2002 No. 200 on its implementation. It can be noted that the "Program for the Development of Informatization and Information and Communication Technologies for 2002-2010" was approved by the decision [2].

Us famous education in system independent education For dedicated hours some in sciences audience watch closer or more certain. Current in a day independent education major improvement tool modern information technologies existence in that ready multimedia study material education recipient independent knowledge important to get tool existence service does. Multimedia interactive educational materials - in fact education receivers For independent knowledge get by creating give With together received knowledge control also creates opportunities to do.

The basis of the modern education system is a high-quality and high-tech environment, as well as its creation, development in technical and program terms. difficult, however such Wednesday education improve the system education to the process information And communication technologies current achieve through knowledge efficiency enlargement service does [4]. Current in a day Not only in education Maybe All information in the fields technologies current what is being done Let's see possible In particular that's all until the day In our republic 50 To near law And solutions exactly information technologies field development And in the

fields related to introduction.

Multimedia interactive study to materials be placed basic requirement his last the science achievements level data secured And learning modern methods using education recipient Sciences essence full understand from ensuring that comprises From this except another interesting control of the student's knowledge through the use of tools through tests, crossword puzzles and bliss-questions when studying a multimedia manual efficiency Ascending service does. Multimedia that the student fully understands the information on the topics when creating the learning material For study material systematized to present achieve, use information in different formats (text, audio, animation, video) reasonable.

On the topics of creating and using e-learning resources and multimedia applications Martin Schmucker, Vannimer Bush Robert Zehetmayer, Armando Cirrincione, Omar El-Gayar Qing Li, Subramanyam Vdaygiri , Stuart Goose, Steve Clarke, Henk M. Blanken, Arjen P. De Vries, Henk Ernst block, ling feng, TPKatunin, D. Leshchev, V. V. Lipaev, U. Sh. Begimkulov, F. M. Zakirova, K.T.Olimov, U. Yu. Yuldashev, U. Mukhamedkhanov, O. Rasulov and many other scientists and scientific researchers conduct various scientific studies.

Multimedia technologies information majority famous and from promising directions Counts They are as part of images collection, sound, video, animation and another interactive conjugate and other control mechanisms was visual effective texts and data product create target did The idea of the emergence of multimedia technologies was proposed by the American scientist Vannevar Bush in 1945 [9].

Multimedia modern information technologies as a result the science O assumption imagination such as concepts modern variety technical tool and programs through gives out to the left. Thanks to modern information technologies such as text, video, animation, graphics, holography information species using human education take electronic interactive educational materials have been created that serve to increase the effectiveness of training (Fig. 1) [1].

Figure 1

Multimedia – this computer technology another another technical and software resources using famous look to have from available information use with depends on concepts Considered Technical and software resources, and quality information in the preparation of multimedia applications necessity will now new technical tool and innovative multimedia programs are widely used (Fig. 2).

Figure 2

Another of the modern multimedia technologies used in the educational process is interactive electronic boards. They look like ordinary whiteboards with markers, and every text, graphic, drawing, table, etc. written on them. appears on the whiteboard display in a very short time [6].

Electronic in the use of multimedia technology The main advantages of blackboards in education:

- ❖ Assembly Hall student's attention one object orientation;
- ❖ The presence of options for copying, sending by e-mail, saving the results related to the topic of the lesson;
- ❖ Lesson in progress text, sound, animation, from graphics breadth of public access;
- ❖ Subject explanation in progress information editing the possibility of using an electronic pen [8].

Multimedia software mainly includes graphic programs, audio and video programs and this audio, video and the graph can be specified by the editing program [11].

Examples of sound recording programs include sound recording and sound recording programs. To edit sound data, programs such as FL Studio, Sound editor.

Graphics programs create and process information that is the basis of multimedia programs. It is an electronic photo editing program for Macintosh and IBM PC computers running Windows. Adobe Photoshop is manufactured by Adobe System Inc. and is known for its ease of use [11].

Presentation software: A group of programs can be distinguished from the presentation software package used in Macintosh and Windows environments. IN this group includes Freelance Graphics from Lotus, Harvard Graphics from Software Publishing, Power Point from Microsoft. The developers of these programs increase the tools used in each new version and expand the possibilities of use.

If the user has sufficient knowledge of programming languages, AutoPlay Media Studio offers a wide range of possibilities. In combination with a good idea, together with creative and diverse specialists (designers, photographers, video operators, etc.), it is possible to create a high-quality, professional and competitive product.

Education to the system new pedagogical technologies application achieve each other filler

two on a bilateral basis process existence one from the side teaching profession activity technologies If second from the side student knowledge get activation based from technology consists of Innovation (English) – innovations innovation, innovation within this system.

High-quality and high-tech environment is the basis of the modern education system organize enough. His Creation and development technical complex, but such an environment serves to improve the educational system, the introduction of information and communication technologies in the educational process [10].

Multimedia technologies - allow you to use several ways of presenting information at the same time: text, graphics, animation, video, sound, etc.

Multimedia products can be divided into the following groups:	Content of the multimedia product
Encyclopedias	Two and three-dimensional images
Educational programs	Soundtrack
Mindfulness Programs	Music
E-books	Animation
Programs for children	Video
Games and more	Text and numeric information, etc.

Last for year’s multimedia products wide buyers reached the level to which it was possible. Their usage is not always the same. Different multimedia equipment buy When receiving, you need to pay attention to the following indicators:

- the quality and reliability of the material provided;
- the quality of the provided graphic material;
- sound accompaniment (text, musical arrangement, etc.);
- availability of video materials and their quality;
- interactivity capabilities (viewing in different directions, in-depth study of the material, the ability to print, etc.);
- friendly interface.

Multimedia product - containing music, video clips, animation, Pictures and slides gallery, another data bases and others entrance possible was interactive. on the computer is a finished product [7]

Electronic learning systems are being created and their new types and forms.

These new types are distinguished by the following qualities:

1) e-learning systems are built as an electronic analogue of paper textbooks. Automated textbooks, reference books, etc. fit this explanation;

2) in e-learning systems, the computer performs technical functions, and not the functions of learning tools. This will lead to more versatile, compact and relatively inexpensive training and laboratory training systems.

3) e-learning systems are focused on targeted educational activities and activities. This led to the separation of multimedia lectures, automated tests, etc.;

4) e-learning systems are adapted to the pedagogical tasks solved with their help. This aspect corresponds to automated retraining courses, knowledge control systems, etc.

Currently, the following four reasons can be identified that impede the widespread creation and dissemination of e-learning systems:

1) the fact that the existing educational system is not yet fully ready for the active use of

electronic learning tools, their integration into the educational process and their organization on the existing technological base;

- 2) insufficient level of qualified specialists;
- 3) lack of developed methodology;
- 4) a large amount of financial costs for the mass creation and distribution of e-learning systems [3].

In conclusion, today there is a point of view that the development of e-learning systems is one of the most complex and complex issues, and its implementation is more like creativity than technology. In general, the creation of e-learning systems is seen as a complex, time-consuming and expensive process.

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